

CREEP OF EXPANDED CLAY CONCRETE UNDER COMPRESSION AND TENSION

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Abstract. The paper presents a method for experimentally determining the creep of expanded clay concrete under compression and tension. The results of determining the deformation and the measure of creep, and the previous loading on the strength and modulus of elasticity of expanded clay concrete, as well as the kinetics of changes in the deformation and measure of creep of expanded clay concrete over time under compression and tension are obtained. The measures of expanded clay concrete creep in tension are compared with the measure of creep in compression, and empirical formulas for their description and functions $m(t; \tau_1)$ are proposed, taking into account the influence of the previous loading.

Keywords: expanded clay concrete, strength, elasticity model, creep, creep measure, axial compression and tension, previous loading.

INTRODUCTION

The main characteristics of concrete taken into account in the calculations are the strength and modulus of elasticity of concrete at the time of application of force and temperature-humidity effects, the measure of creep (creep characteristic) of concrete, deformation of concrete shrinkage, etc. Currently, the problem of creating

and researching mechanical models of reinforced concrete that adequately reflect such characteristic properties of the material as creep and shrinkage is undoubtedly relevant [1-4].

In connection with the desire to lighten the weight of structures, studies of the nature of the deformability of expanded clay concrete, in particular, creep, are of particular relevance. The creep value is the most important parameter taken into account when designing prestressed reinforced concrete structures. The creep of concrete has a strong influence on the distribution of forces in statically indeterminate systems, concrete and reinforced concrete dams, bridges of large spans [5-11].

Other well-known models for predicting the creep in designed structures include the European model 1990 Comite Euro-International du Beton (1990 CEB) [12] and the simplified BP (Bazant-Panula) model [13]. The 1990 CEB model is similar to the ACI Committee 209 model [14] and, in predicting the creep, it takes into account the factors of loading age, loading duration, cement type, ambient relative humidity, structure thickness and size. One of the basic differences between this model and the ACI Committee 209 model [14] is that it considers concrete strength as one of the variables in creep prediction. The second basic difference is that the influence of the ambient relative humidity and the size and thickness of the structure on the degree of creep is considered in addition to the influence of these variables on the total or ultimate creep. Failure to consider the influence of these factors on the degree of creep is a shortcoming of the ACI Committee 209 model [14].

The currently available works do not contain exhaustive answers to a number of questions related to the calculation of the strength of bent elements made of light concrete, with the lack of creep data. Many important issues of design and calculation of expanded clay concrete structures due to the difficulties of creating a complete theory of their deformation and destruction are solved approximately, on an empirical or semi-empirical basis. The widespread use of artificial porous aggregates instead of natural heavy aggregates is a determining condition for increasing the efficiency of capital investments in the construction of transport and other critical structures [2, 5].

METHODS

The composition and main characteristics of concrete are given in Tables 1 and 2. Expanded clay gravel of two fractions 5–10 and 10–20 mm in a ratio of 40:60 was taken as a coarse aggregate produced in the Tashkent cement plant. As Portland cement, the cement of the Navoi cement plant was used, and the sand of the Tashkent quarry was used as quartz sand.

TABLE 1. Composition of expanded clay concrete (EC)

Actual consumption of materials per m^3 of concrete	cement, kg	427
	sand, kg	629
	expanded clay, kg (l)	414 (727)
W/C (water/cement ratio)		0.49

TABLE 2. Characteristics of expanded clay concrete

Bulk density of dry expanded clay concrete, kg/m^3	1760
Cubic strength, R, MPa	33.0
Prism strength, R_b , MPa	28.4
Prism strength factor, R_b/R	0.86
Initial modulus of elasticity, E_b , Pa	15.4

Note: Specimens were tested at the age of 28 days. Prisms dimensions - 150x150x600 mm, cubes ribs - 150 mm. The cone slump of concrete mix - 1...2 cm.

Loading of samples at stress levels of $0.3R_b$ and $0.3R_{bt}$, compression and tension was carried out, respectively, in spring and lever installations with a maximum force of 210 kN and 30 kN.

During the compression test, the prism samples were installed with 30 cm thick metal support plates glued to the ends with ball joints, and the tensile sample cylinders were installed in the installation using collet grips and Hook joints (Fig.1). When loading into the installation, two samples were installed.

When installing two prisms, metal plates 20 mm thick were laid between them, and when installing two cylinders, a Hooke hinge was laid. The load value was set

according to the range of springs, pre-calibrated on the press, on which the short-term loading was conducted.

The range of spring during calibration was measured with PAO-6 deflection meters with a division value of 0.01 mm, installed on two opposite sides (generatrices) of springs.

To eliminate the error associated with non-additivity of shrinkage and creep, before loading, the specimens were waterproofed from the sides with a layer of paraffin 2–3 mm thick and two layers of polyethylene film, gluing the seams with insulating tape.

Fig.1. Long-term testing of samples for compression (a) and tension (b)

In order to separate the elastic and inelastic components of the total strain, the specimens were loaded in steps of 0.10 of the breaking load with staying on the steps to a given level of compressive and tensile stresses until the increase in strain ceased. Under compression tests, the specimens were loaded with a hydraulic jack installed between the upper support plates of the spring installations, controlling the force with deflectometers mounted on three sides of the installation. After reaching the specified force, the corresponding parts (thrust nuts) were fixed and during the entire experiment, the readings of the deflectometers were constantly monitored. The decrease in the compressive force in time, due to the creep strain in specimens, was compensated by periodic additional loading to the initial level. In the tests, the stress drop in the specimens did not exceed 1 MPa, which is 0.05% of the specified level. The error in measuring the forces in the specimens was ± 0.01 MPa.

In the process of testing, to measure the longitudinal deformations of the samples, dial gauges were used, of the type with a division value of 0.01 mm or 0.001 mm, installed with the help of metal frames stationary on four faces of a prism on a base of 150 mm.

To take into account deformations associated with minor changes in temperature and humidity in the room, unloaded isolated twin samples were used. Simultaneously with the measurement of the deformations of the samples placed under a long-term constant load, the deformations of the unloaded twin samples were measured to determine the shrinkage deformation.

Before the samples loaded with a long-acting load, their twins were tested in a similar way on a press with a short-term load until failure. At the same time, the cubes were tested.

The samples were tested under load for 210 days, and then they were unloaded and the deformation effects were measured for 56 days. With the expiration of 56 days after unloading, the main and reference samples were brought to failure under a short-term action of compressive load. The modulus of elasticity and compressive strength were determined to estimate the value of function $m(t, \tau_1) = R'/R \cong E'/E$ (where R', R, E', E – are the strength and elastic modulus of the main and reference samples, respectively), which takes into account the effect of the previous loading of the material on the short-term strength and elastic modulus.

Creep strains under compression and tension were calculated taking into account the strains that occur during staying under short-term stepwise loading of samples to a given stress level.

In these studies, the verification of the homogeneity of concrete and the selection of groups of twin samples were given the most serious attention. Nevertheless, despite the careful selection of groups of twin samples, the scatter of experimental data in time to failure turned out to be quite significant. In this regard, it was necessary to abandon the assessment of test results "by groups" and switch to individual samples. The "actual" level of stresses in concrete was refined on the basis of a joint analysis of strain curves " $\eta-\sigma_x$ " obtained when the samples were long-term

loaded and available "reference" curves " $\eta-\sigma_x$ " obtained during a short-term test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The kinetics of changes in the measure of creep in expanded clay concrete in time under axial compression and tension are shown in Fig. 2, and shrinkage strains are shown in Fig. 3. The growth of curves of the creep measure of the specimens have the greatest rise at the initial time after the load application (30 days), then there is a slight decrease in the growth of the creep measure with a tendency to stabilization. It can be assumed that the intensive development of the creep measure in the first days after the load application is due to significant structural strains in concrete.

Fig.2. Kinetics of the change in the creep measure of expanded clay concrete over time during axial tension (1) and compression (2)

Fig.3. Kinetics of changes in shrinkage deformation of expanded clay concrete over time

Figures 2–3 show the calculated curves plotted using one of the equations (1) of

the theory of an elastic-creeping body, obtained on the basis of a modification of the of N.Kh. Arutyunyan theory of an elastic-creeping body with the core [15]. The results obtained indicate good convergence of the calculated curves with the experimental data (the discrepancy is no more than 10%).

In [16], the following dependence was proposed to determine the relative strain of the nonlinear creep in expanded clay concrete:

$$\varepsilon_{x,p}(t; \tau_1) = (\sigma_{bl} + \alpha\sigma_{bl}^3)C_b(t; \tau_1) \quad (1)$$

where σ_{bl} is the working stress, MPa;

α is a numerical coefficient determined from tests;

$C_b(t; \tau_1)$ is a measure of linear creep in expanded clay concrete, which can be determined by the dependence proposed in [16].

For the numerical solution of equation (1), it is necessary to determine the values of the short-term strength limit under axial compression and tension and the creep measures $C_b(t; \tau_1)$, $C_{bt}(t; \tau_1)$, its change in time, and the values of the modulus of elasticity and functions $m(t; \tau_1)$.

The values of the measure of linear creep in the mortar part of expanded clay concrete under axial tension (if there are no direct experimental data) are determined by formula (3):

$$C_{bt}^*(t; \tau_1) = \lambda(t; \tau_1)C_b(t; \tau_1); \quad (2)$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{70R_b^2(\tau_1 - 2) + 13000R_b - 140000}{(177R_b - 1700)R_b\tau_1^{3/2}} 10^{-5} \\ &+ \frac{0,2R_b + 15\tau_1 - 0,2R_b + 100}{R_b} [1 \\ &- e^{-\gamma(t-\tau_1)}] 10^{-5}; \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\gamma_1 = 0,015 + 18/R_b; \quad (4)$$

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the second factor in formula (4) is taken into account at $\tau_1 > 16$ days.

$$\lambda(t; \tau_1) = a + \frac{b(t; \tau_1)}{t_1}. \quad (5)$$

for expanded clay concrete of dense structure (on quartz sand):

$$a = 2.15; \quad b = 0.63 \quad \text{at } 0 < (t - \tau_1) \leq 2 \text{ days.}$$

$$a = 3.40; \quad b = -0.077 \quad \text{at } 2 < (t - \tau_1) \leq 15 \text{ days.}$$

$$a = 2.25; \quad b = -0.03 \quad \text{at } 15 < (t - \tau_1) \leq 100 \text{ days.}$$

$$a = 2.00; \quad b = 0 \quad \text{at } (t - \tau_1) > 100 \text{ days.}$$

for expanded clay concrete of porous structure (on expanded clay sand):

$$a = 2.0; \quad b = 1.0 \quad \text{at } 0 < (t - \tau_1) \leq 2 \text{ days.}$$

$$a = 4.06; \quad b = 0.03 \quad \text{at } 2 < (t - \tau_1) \leq 100 \text{ days.}$$

$$a = 1.0; \quad b = 0 \quad \text{at } (t - \tau_1) > 100 \text{ days.}$$

The values of function $m(t; \tau_1)$, taking into account the effect of a long-term loading on the change in the surface energy of the material in the crack zone for expanded clay concrete, are calculated by formula (6)

$$m(t; \tau_1) = a_1 + b_1 \lg(t - \tau_1), \quad (6)$$

where $a_1 = 1.091; \quad b_1 = 0.035$ at $\tau_1 \leq 28$ days,

$a_1 = 1.033; \quad b_1 = 0.029$ at $\tau_1 > 28$ days.

The value of the function $m(t; \tau_1)$ at the intensity of the previous compressive and tensile stresses was 1.09 and 1.10 in strength, respectively, and 1.05 and 1.08 in modulus of elasticity.

The results of determining the values of the functions $m(t; \tau_1)$ show that at stresses $(0.3)R_b$, the increase in strength (modulus of elasticity) during compression and tension was 9% (5%) and 10% (8%), respectively, which is confirmed by the

conclusions [15, 17,19].

The increase in the strength of compressed and stretched concrete can be explained by the removal of internal, redistribution of stresses between structural elements, which in turn equalizes the stress field due to the ongoing physico-chemical processes of hardening of cement stone, as well as some compaction of the concrete structure.

Due to the fact that the data on the study of creep in concrete with porous aggregates under axial tension are very limited, we compared the measures of creep in expanded clay concrete under axial compression and tension to specify the pattern of change in their relationship in time. It can be seen that the value of the ratio of the indicated values of the creep measure changes according to a curvilinear law depending on the observation period (Fig. 4).

This confirms the conclusions obtained in earlier studies with the mixes on lithoid pumice and expanded clay sands [16]. At the initial observation time $(t; \tau_1) \leq 2$ days, the measure of creep in expanded clay concrete under tension significantly exceeds the measure of creep under compression; then their ratios begin to decrease and at $(t; \tau_1) > 100$ days, it practically stabilizes (Fig. 4).

For calculation, the curve can be divided into four sections and take changes $\lambda(t; \tau_1) = C_{bt}(t; \tau_1)/C_b(t; \tau_1)$, (8) depending on $(t; \tau_1)$ according to a linear law in each section:

Fig.4. Comparison of the measure of creep in expanded clay concrete under axial tension and compression

The values obtained in the experiments for measures of creep in expanded clay concrete under tension and compression and their ratios $C_{bt}(t; \tau_1)/C_b(t; \tau_1)$ at the age $(t-\tau_1) > 100$ days are given in Table 2, which shows that the measure of creep in expanded clay concrete under tension is approximately 2 times greater than under compression.

R.K. Zhitkevich, in his study in [18], analyzing experimental data and summarizing the results of other researchers, reports that the creep strain in structural expanded clay concrete is 1.3 ... 3.0 times greater than that of equal-strength heavy concrete (with equal absolute values of stresses).

CONCLUSIONS

An empirical formula for the definition and description, convenient for practical application, is obtained:

- the measures of linear creep in expanded clay concrete under axial tension and compression (if there are no direct experimental data) (2, 3);
- the pattern of change in $\lambda(t; \tau_1) = C_{bt}(t; \tau_1)/C_b(t; \tau_1)$, (8) depending on $(t; \tau_1)$ according to a linear law in each section (5);
- the pattern of effect of the previous loading on the strength and modulus of elasticity of concrete (6);

2. It has been experimentally proved that at previous stresses $(0.3)R_b$, the increase in strength (modulus of elasticity) during compression and tension was 9% (5%) and 10% (8%), respectively.

It was determined that the creep strains in expanded clay concrete at an equal relative level of stresses ($\eta = 0.3$) under axial tension exceed the creep strain under compression by about 3.5...4.0 times. It was also revealed that the value of the ratio of the measure of creep under tension to the measure of creep under compression increases intensively at the initial time after loading $(t-\tau_1) \leq 2$ days), then begins to decrease, $(2 \text{ days} < (t-\tau_1) \leq 100 \text{ days})$, and, with the passage of time, at long-term

periods of observation it stabilizes, $(t - \tau_l) > 100$ days.

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